

1 Hidden Neurotoxicity: Re-analysis of an industry study reveals
2 obscured brain developmental effects of fluazinam and failures in EU
3 oversight

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10 Abstract

11 Background: EU law aims to ensure a high level of human health protection. The safety assessment
12 of pesticides relies on studies performed by the producing companies. Regulatory authorities
13 evaluate these studies and draw conclusions that inform the approval or non-approval.

14 Methods: Following up on earlier observations that companies have withheld developmental
15 neurotoxicity (DNT) studies from regulatory agencies, we re-analyzed company-commissioned data
16 regarding brain development in rat offspring after developmental exposure to the fungicide
17 fluazinam. We replicated the test laboratory's statistical methods and refined them to increase their
18 power. We also reviewed the evaluation of this study by regulatory agencies in the EU.

19 Results: We identified six instances of false reporting of statistical results by the company-
20 commissioned test laboratory that collectively mask an effect on brain development in adult
21 offspring. Refined statistical methods revealed an effect of fluazinam on brain weight, brain width,
22 and three linear brain dimensions that had gone unrecognized by EU authorities, although the

23 magnitude of the effect was known to be relevant and the test laboratory's statistical analysis was
24 known to be flawed. Furthermore, the Rapporteur Member State applied a 10% threshold for
25 decreases in brain weight to be considered adverse, which is not protective.

26 Conclusions: A chain of failures prevented the high ambitions for human health protection from
27 being achieved: a 15-year delay in the company's submission of the study, reporting of false
28 statistical results by the test laboratory, application of an overly permissive threshold for adverse
29 effects, and failure by regulatory agencies to perform or request appropriate statistical tests during
30 the "Pesticide Peer Review" process.

31 We conclude that fluazinam likely should not have gained EU approval in 2008 and is unlikely to
32 receive a renewal, due to its DNT properties.

33 We further conclude that the EU pesticide approval system does not reliably provide the intended
34 level of protection, because reporting biases can go undetected through insufficient scrutiny by
35 regulatory agencies.

36 We propose improving human health protection by reducing pesticide use, commissioning future
37 toxicity studies via authorities, and ensuring that regulatory agencies have sufficient resources and
38 capacity to conduct thorough evaluations of industry data and assessments.

39 Key words: Fluazinam, developmental neurotoxicity, regulatory toxicology, food and feed omnibus,
40 plant protection products regulation, safety assessment, pesticides, regulatory risk assessment,
41 Good Laboratory Practice

42 [List of abbreviations](#)

43 AAOEL - acute acceptable operator exposure level

44 ADI - Acceptable Daily Intake

45 AOEL - Acceptable Operator Exposure Level

- 46 ARfD - Acute Reference Dose
- 47 BMR - Benchmark Response Level
- 48 bw - bodyweight
- 49 DNT - Developmental Neurotoxicity
- 50 EFSA - European Food Safety Authority
- 51 EU - European Union
- 52 GLP - Good Laboratory Practice
- 53 HC - Historical Controls
- 54 LOAEL - Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level
- 55 NOAEL - No Observed Adverse Effect Level
- 56 PND - Post Natal Day
- 57 RMS - Rapporteur Member State
- 58

59 Background

60 The developing brain is highly sensitive to chemical insults [1]. Neurodevelopmental processes,
61 including neuronal proliferation, migration, and differentiation, occur within tightly regulated time
62 windows during which disruption may lead to long-term adverse effects in brain function.
63 Consequently, developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) is of high concern in chemical safety assessment.

64 Plant protection products are highly regulated in the European Union (EU), requiring comprehensive,
65 pre-market testing and safety evaluation. The rationale is that their use poses significant
66 environmental and health risks, as they are extensively applied and intentionally designed to be
67 biologically active, and often highly toxic, to target organisms.

68 The EU legislation aims to ensure a high level of protection for human health, including vulnerable
69 populations such as fetuses, infants, and children. The Plant Protection Products Regulation
70 1107/2009 requires that plant protection products “shall have no immediate or delayed harmful
71 effect on human health, including that of vulnerable groups” [2]. This reflects the general
72 precautionary objectives set out in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union [3].

73 As a means of protecting the developing brain, the legislation includes a hazard-based cut-off
74 criterion for substances presumed to be toxic to human reproduction, which includes developmental
75 neurotoxicity. Substances with such properties cannot be permitted for use in plant protection
76 products. The legislation also identifies developmental neurotoxicity and effects on the the immune
77 system, as endpoints of particular concern that motivate an increased margin of safety.

78 To evaluate DNT, active substances may be subjected to toxicity studies conducted according to
79 internationally accepted test guidelines, such as OECD technical guideline 426 [4].

80 These studies involve exposure of pregnant animals during gestation and lactation, thereby exposing
81 offspring during critical periods of nervous system development. Endpoints include developmental
82 landmarks, behavioral assessments, brain weight measurements, and quantitative morphometric

83 measurements of the size of several brain regions in offspring. Such studies are designed to detect
84 adverse effects that are not captured by adult toxicity testing and may therefore play an important
85 role in hazard identification, safety evaluations and regulatory decision-making.

86 The safety evaluation of plant protection products depends fundamentally on the reliability and
87 completeness of toxicological data submitted by manufacturers to regulatory authorities. In the EU,
88 regulatory evaluations rely predominantly on studies commissioned and funded by the
89 manufacturers seeking market authorization. To safeguard scientific reliability and prevent fraud,
90 regulatory studies must be conducted under Good Laboratory Practice (GLP) rules, which impose
91 requirements for study conduct and documentation, data integrity, quality assurance and the use of
92 appropriate laboratory equipment [5,6].

93 Regulatory assessment is not a one-time exercise but a recurring process involving industry dossier
94 preparation, evaluation by Rapporteur Member States (RMS), and peer review by other member
95 states and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). Reassessments are required because
96 scientific knowledge evolve over time. Consequently, non-renewal of active substances is not
97 uncommon; substances may lose approval because newly recognized adverse effects are detected,
98 previously available findings are reinterpreted considering updated scientific understanding, or
99 regulatory standards or data requirements are revised.

100 These evaluations are resource-intensive, time-consuming, and scientifically demanding for both
101 applicant companies and regulatory authorities. Proposals have emerged to simplify the regulatory
102 framework, including suggestions for time-unlimited approvals of active substances, as discussed in
103 current “food and feed omnibus” proposal [7].

104 This proposal implicitly assumes that the evidentiary basis for authorization is complete, reliable,
105 and transparently disclosed to regulatory authorities. In contrast, our previous work has raised
106 concerns about the reliability and completeness of industry-submitted data and assessments. We
107 identified inaccurate or incomplete reporting of developmental neurotoxicity findings, that

108 contributed to obscuring regulatory evidence of adverse neurodevelopmental effects [8].
109 Subsequent analyses documented failures to disclose relevant toxicity studies to regulatory
110 authorities, thereby undermining legally required safety assessments [9,10]. The suppression of
111 product-safety findings that are unfavorable to a company's commercial interests, including
112 withholding or avoiding publication of research and distortion or minimization of adverse health
113 effects, has indeed been observed across multiple industries [11,12].

114 Taken together, these findings suggest that weaknesses in the regulation of plant protection
115 products may involve systematic deficiencies in reporting practices, transparency, and regulatory
116 compliance.

117 An especially serious concern arises when unfavorable toxicological findings are not merely
118 underreported or omitted, but actively concealed. Concealment or misrepresentation of adverse
119 findings may distort hazard characterization, bias safety assessments, prevent regulators from
120 identifying real risks and hence result in insufficient protection of human health. In the context of
121 developmental neurotoxicity assessment, suppression of adverse findings may be particularly
122 consequential because it undermines regulatory safeguards specifically intended to protect
123 vulnerable populations including children.

124 Fluazinam

125 Fluazinam is a fungicide, and its re-approval in the EU is currently under evaluation. Its
126 representative use, evaluated in the Assessment Report, compiled by Rapporteur Member State
127 (RMS) Austria for the EU, is the control of the fungus *Phytophthora infestans* that causes late blight
128 in potatoes [13]. The main dietary sources are apples and pears [14], with chronic dietary exposures
129 below 1% of the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of 0.01 mg/kg bodyweight (bw)/day for all population
130 groups. Exposure for residents is higher; the intended use of one of three fluazinam products
131 included in the Assessment Report exceeded the Acceptable Operator Exposure Level (AOEL) for
132 resident children (0.004 mg/kg bw/day). Exposure estimates for residents in apple or pear producing

133 regions are part of national product authorizations and thus not included in the EU Assessment
134 Report. Fluazinam is frequently used in apple production in Southern Tyrol, and has been among the
135 most frequently detected pesticide at children's playground and in altitudinal transects in that
136 region [15,16], so exposure of residents is highly likely.

137 The active substance fluazinam was among nine compounds for which applicant companies had
138 failed to disclose an existing DNT study to EU authorities, despite legal requirements [10]. During the
139 renewal process of the approval for fluazinam, initiated in 2016 and still ongoing, the study was
140 requested from the applicant company. In the initial evaluation by RMS Austria in 2021, it was
141 concluded that the study was negative, i.e. no DNT effects were identified. In October 2023, we sent
142 a letter to EFSA pointing out potential effects of fluazinam on the brain weight of adult offspring
143 (post natal day (PND 66), observed at the two highest dose levels and potentially also at the lowest
144 dose [13].

145 In the most recent update to the regulatory assessment, from 2025, it was concluded that fluazinam
146 is a developmental neurotoxicant, based on effects observed at the highest dose tested on brain
147 weight, brain width, and the auditory startle reflex in young offspring (PND 21/22), with the brain
148 width effect persisting into adulthood (PND 66) [17,18]. An effect on brain weight in adult offspring
149 was negated.

150 In the present study, we re-analyze the quantitative data regarding adult offspring brains reported in
151 the guideline DNT study of fluazinam [19], performed 2003-2004 at Huntingdon Life Sciences,
152 England. We replicated the test laboratories statistical analyses and performed own additional
153 analyses in line with the recommendations developed during the evaluation process so far, with the
154 purpose of making an independent evaluation of the DNT findings.

155 **Methods**

156 **Data**

157 The data used in this work were obtained from the industry-funded guideline developmental
158 neurotoxicity (DNT) study report of the pesticide active substance fluazinam [19], performed 2003-
159 2004 at Huntingdon Life Sciences, Ltd., Huntingdon, Cambridgeshire, England. The study was
160 commissioned by Ishihara Sangyo Kaisha, Ltd. (ISK), Osaka, Japan.

161 The DNT study was performed in accordance with U.S. EPA OPPTS guideline 870.6300. In short,
162 groups of 24 pregnant female rats were administered doses of 0 (control), 2, 10 or 50 mg
163 fluazinam/kg bodyweight/day by gavage from gestational day 6 until lactational day 20/21. In
164 addition, their offspring was dosed by gavage from PND 7 to PND 20/21, due to low lactational
165 transfer.

166 Examination of offspring included various brain parameters (weight, length, width, and linear
167 morphometrics in four regions – all at PND 21 and PND 66), behavioural testing (motor activity at
168 PND 13, 17, 21, 60; auditory startle at PND 23/24 and 58; and learning and memory on PND 23/24
169 and 61). In addition, a variety of other parameters were also evaluated, including litter data, clinical
170 signs, body weight (gain), sexual maturation, a functional observational battery, necropsy and
171 pathology.

172 The data analysis in the present article focused on quantitative data for PND 66 brains in offspring.

173 Two sets of brain samples were generated in this study for PND 66 offspring:

174 (a) from perfused animals; n=11-13 pups/sex/dose group. These were used to obtain measurements
175 for brain weight, length and width as well as for morphometry. Among these, each litter contributed
176 one male or one female i.e. no two pups were from the same litter. (b) from non-perfused animals; n
177 = 42-49 pups/sex/dose group. These were used for brain weight measurements only. Among these,
178 in most cases, each litter contributed with 2 males and 2 females.

179 Raw data were extracted from the study report by optical character recognition (Adobe Acrobat Pro
180 version 2026.001) and manually. The following parts were used as data sources: Appendix 93 (brain
181 weight PND 66 non-perfused offspring), Appendix 94 (brain weight PND66 perfused offspring),
182 Appendix 95 (brain length and width PND 66 perfused offspring), Appendix 96 (brain morphometry
183 PND66 perfused offspring). Extracted data were verified by calculating summary statistics (means
184 and standard deviations by sex and dose group) (Table 1), and comparing these to the corresponding
185 values included in the study report. This comparison was done by two persons independently. Any
186 discrepancies were resolved through manual inspection of raw data.

187 [Statistics](#)

188 We initially (a) replicated the statistical analyses included in the study report regarding these
189 endpoints. We then (b) performed own analyses in order to increase statistical power and obtain
190 valid tests for clustered data. All data analyses were performed in R v. 4.6.0 [20], using RStudio v.
191 2026.04.0 (Posit) as code editor.

192 The study report prescribes parametric analysis for datasets if (a) less than 75% of the data points
193 have the same value and (b) Bartlett's test for heteroscedasticity is $p \geq 0.01$. These requirements
194 were fulfilled by most datasets included in this article, except for brain weight in non-perfused
195 animals for which Bartlett's test indicated heteroscedasticity. An in-house test at the test laboratory,
196 referred to as "HEALEY, G.F. (1999) The F_1 approximate parametric test for monotonicity. Internal
197 Technical Information Document ST9725, Department of Statistics, Huntingdon Life Sciences", was
198 used to decide if Dunnett's or Williams' test should be used in parametric tests. To our knowledge,
199 this " F_1 " test has not been published in the scientific literature, and it is not available to us. Where
200 relevant, we used Spearman's rank correlation as a substitute, and report in the text which of
201 Williams' and Dunnett's tests was indicated through presence ($p < 0.05$) or absence of a significant
202 correlation in Spearman's test. Nonetheless, we performed and reported results from both

203 Dunnett's and Williams' test, referring to the tests as primary and secondary analysis, depending on
204 Spearman's rank correlation. In case of heteroscedasticity, the use of Shirley's test was prescribed.
205 Dunnett's test compares each of multiple dose levels against a control group, and controls the
206 family-wise error rate [21,22]. It does not assume any particular dose-response relationship.
207 Williams' test is a step-wise procedure to identify the "minimum effective dose" in monotonic dose-
208 response relationships, that also controls the family-wise error rate but is more powerful compared
209 to Dunnett's test in such situations [23,24]. Williams' test compares a t' statistic against a critical
210 value, resulting in acceptance or rejection of a null hypothesis at $\alpha=0.05$, rather than a p-value.
211 Shirley's test [25] is a non-parametric adaption of Williams' test using rank-based statistic.

212 **(a) Replication of statistical analysis of datasets using original methods**

213 Datasets regarding perfused PND66 offspring brain weight and brain morphometrics were re-
214 analysed using the statistical methods specified in the study report. No sensitivity analyses were
215 performed.

216 **(b) new original analyses of the same datasets**

217 None of the data analytical procedures in the original study report has included sex as a factor;
218 instead, data have consistently been analysed separately for sexes. This constitutes an unnecessary
219 loss of statistical power in a situation where power is already known to be low. Guidance has
220 recommended to include sex as a factor thereby increasing the number of animals in the statistical
221 analysis [26], and specifically for brain weight analysis in the DNT study of fluazinam, we [13] and the
222 EFSA Working Group for Neurotoxicity [17] have suggested that such analysis would be helpful.
223 Methods were thus chosen to include sex as a fixed factor and, where relevant, litter as a random
224 factor in statistical models, whilst otherwise following the methods specified in the study report as
225 closely and as reasonably as possible.

226 Accordingly, it is a deliberate design choice to adapt Williams' test to situations that it was not
227 originally intended for, in particular regarding the presence of two factors (dose and sex) and of
228 clustered data. Similarly, while Dunnett's test is robust and valid in the present analyses, it is not the
229 most sensitive test in the presence of a monotonic dose-response trend. The use of these methods is
230 intended to constitute a simple but relevant improvement of the methods employed by the test
231 laboratory, that could have easily been requested or implemented during the authorities' review of
232 the study without the need to develop and argue for the use of different methods. The use of these
233 methods does thus not constitute a conclusion that they are the most relevant or suitable ones,
234 which would be outside the scope for this paper.

235 Linear fixed-effects and mixed-effects models were built using the package nlme v. 3.1-169 [27].
236 Initial models included fixed factors sex and dose. Inclusion of a sex*dose interaction effect, and of
237 heteroscedasticity using a weights argument, was sequentially tested, and retained if indicated by an
238 anova() test against the simpler model, and by comparing AIC and BIC of the two models. Initial and
239 final models were evaluated for normality of residuals using qq-plots and Shapiro-Wilks test. The
240 litter was included as a random factor for tests involving datasets that included more than one pup
241 per litter. Dunnett's test of dose levels against control was implemented using the glht() function in
242 the package multcomp v. 1.4-30 [28]. If the sex*dose interaction was included, Dunnett's test of
243 dose levels against control was based on customized contrasts that accounted for sex-specific
244 coefficient estimates.

245 Williams test for the minimum effective dose in monotonic dose-response curves was performed
246 using the williamsTest() function in the package PMCMRplus v. 1.9.12 [29]. This resembles the
247 originally described Williams' test as also referred to in the study report. For evaluating the normal
248 distribution assumption for Williams' test, qq-plots and Shapiro-Wilks test were performed using
249 residuals from a one-way linear model based on the same factor. Williams' test does not
250 accommodate the inclusion of an additional fixed factor such as sex. For analyses of perfused

251 offspring where no two animals were from the same litter, we thus pooled data for males and
252 females, without scaling or adjustment. This constitutes a loss of statistical power due to variability
253 between sexes that is unaccounted for in the test. Slight sex imbalances across dose groups may, on
254 the other hand, slightly exaggerate differences between dose groups and control. We therefore
255 included several sensitivity analyses for such tests:

256 1. Williams' test was performed on dose level summary statistics (sex-balanced means and pooled
257 residual standard deviations extracted from the same linear model that also was the basis for
258 Dunnett's test); summary statistics were supplied to `williamsTest()` as a reconstructed dataset.

259 2. additionally allowing for heteroscedasticity in the linear model;

260 3. using Williams'-like contrasts in the `glht()` function) in the R package `multcomp` for the linear
261 model developed for Dunnett's test. This test differs from the original Williams' test, in spite of the
262 name [30], but both tests share the contrasts, assume monotonicity, and perform step-down tests.

263 For the analysis of non-perfused offspring with multiple pups per sex from the same litter, Williams'
264 test was performed on sex-balanced litter means of brain weights, thus avoiding the inclusion of
265 these factors. Brain weights were first averaged for each sex and each litter; then, the mean of
266 females and males constituted the litter mean. Litters without males or without females were
267 excluded in this analysis. Only sensitivity analysis 3 was performed.

268 Shirley's test was performed with the `shirleyWilliamsTest()` function in the package `PMCMRplus`. The
269 function uses asymptotic t' -crit, which is an appropriate approximation for the samples sizes in the
270 situations this test was used.

271 Data were visualized using the R package `ggplot2` v. 4.0.3 [31].

272 [Use of generative AI](#)

273 Claude Opus 4.7 was used for assisting in writing R code. ChatGTP with GPT-5.5 Instant was used for
274 editing language for grammar and clarity.

275 Results

276 All results refer to adult offspring on PND 66. All results are also from perfused offspring with 10-13
277 animals per sex per dose group, except for one dataset on brain weight that is based on non-
278 perfused offspring, with 42-49 animals per sex per dose group. (A perfused animal is an animal in
279 which saline and fixative are circulated through the bloodstream after euthanasia to remove blood
280 and rapidly preserve tissues, improving brain histology and morphometric analysis in DNT studies.)

281 Figure 1 summarizes data from the largest brain weight dataset included in the DNT study report, i.e.
282 non-perfused animals with data from approximately 4 pups (2 males and 2 females) per litter and 24
283 litters per dose group. Several observations can be made:

- 284 • In both sexes, brain weight monotonically decreases with dose across all dose levels tested,
285 with similar effect magnitudes.
- 286 • Pups from several litters show a brain weight below the control group range already at the
287 lowest dose level tested.
- 288 • A higher data variability is indicated in dosed groups compared to control in both sexes.

289 In the following, this apparent treatment-related effect on the brain in adult offspring is further
290 evaluated quantitatively.

291

292 Figure 1. Boxplot for brain weights (g) in non-perfused PND 66 offspring. Each data point represents the mean of brain
 293 weights within a litter. 22-24 litters per dose group per sex. n=2 animals/litter, in a small number of exceptions n=1 or 3.
 294 Slight jitter applied in the x direction to display overlaying datapoints. Line inside box – median, boxes – 25-75 percentile,
 295 whiskers extend to farthest datapoint still within 1.5* interquartile range. Y-axes have the same scale (length per unit) but
 296 are shifted.

297 Brain weight - perfused offspring

298 Table 1 shows summary statistics for the brain weights of perfused animals. Table 95 of the DNT

299 study report displays these results, with the statement “p≥0.05, no statistical significance”.

dose	Males			Females		
	n(animals)	n(litters)	mean ± SD	n(animals)	n(litters)	mean ± SD
Brain weight – perfused offspring						
0	13	13	2.068 ± 0.062	11	11	1.97 ± 0.117
2	12	12	2.065 ± 0.132	12	12	1.9 ± 0.074
10	12	12	1.996 ± 0.102	11	11	1.915 ± 0.069
50	11	11	1.98 ± 0.154*	12	12	1.837 ± 0.094*
Brain weight – non-perfused offspring						
0	46	24	2.11 ± 0.07	49	24	1.96 ± 0.07
2	48	24	2.08 ± 0.1	48	24	1.93 ± 0.1*
10	43	22	2.04 ± 0.09*	42	22	1.89 ± 0.09*
50	45	23	2.01 ± 0.11*	45	22	1.87 ± 0.11*
Brain width						
0	12	12	15.6 ± 0.3	11	11	15.08 ± 0.41
2	12	12	15.38 ± 0.32	12	12	14.88 ± 0.39
10	12	12	15.32 ± 0.39*	11	11	14.77 ± 0.38
50	11	11	15.15 ± 0.45*	12	12	14.79 ± 0.49
Brain length						
0	12	12	21.25 ± 0.47	11	11	20.52 ± 0.62
2	12	12	21.21 ± 0.54	12	12	20.69 ± 0.67
10	12	12	21.18 ± 0.62	11	11	20.87 ± 0.57
50	11	11	21.54 ± 0.38	12	12	20.82 ± 0.69
Morphometrics - neocortex						
0	10	10	1.91 ± 0.097	10	10	1.85 ± 0.097
50	10	10	1.825 ± 0.106	10	10	1.788 ± 0.054
Morphometrics - hippocampus						
0	10	10	2.078 ± 0.084	10	10	1.988 ± 0.135
50	10	10	1.925 ± 0.167*	10	10	1.88 ± 0.095
Morphometrics – corpus callosum						
0	10	10	0.286 ± 0.035	10	10	0.292 ± 0.033
50	10	10	0.264 ± 0.06	10	10	0.248 ± 0.027*
Morphometrics - cerebellum						
0	10	10	0.862 ± 0.06	10	10	0.848 ± 0.067

50 | 10 10 0.868 ± 0.088 | 10 10 0.836 ± 0.056

300 *Table 1. Replication of analyses of brain weight, width, length, and morphometrics measures from the DNT study report in*
301 *PND66 offspring, by sex and dose group, recalculated from raw data. n – number, SD – standard deviation. *Asterisks*
302 *indicate statistical significance based on the methods described in the study report. **Bold** indicates statistical significance*
303 *that was falsely not reported in the study report.*

304 We replicated the statistical analysis using the same method. Williams' test (assuming monotonic
305 dose-response) was indicated by Spearman's correlation. In Williams' test, for both females and
306 males, the null hypothesis was rejected for the high dose groups (males: $t' = 1.85$, t' -critical = 1.78,
307 $p < 0.05$; females: $t' = 3.54$, t' -critical = 1.79, $p < 0.05$) but not for lower dose groups. In Dunnett's test
308 (*i.e.* not assuming monotonic dose-response), the brain weight of the female high-dose group was
309 significantly lower than control ($p = 0.002869$). These findings are in conflict with the statistical
310 results reported in the DNT study report, which stated no statistical significance for any sex and dose
311 group.

312 We then modified the statistical analysis to increase the statistical power by including both sexes in
313 the same analysis (Table 2). Williams' test was indicated. A significant difference from control was
314 identified in Williams test at high and mid dose; this result was stable in sensitivity analyses, except
315 that in sensitivity analysis 3, even the lowest dose level was significantly different. In Dunnett's test,
316 only the high dose was identified as significantly different from control.

Dose mg/kg /day	Estimates (sex-averaged)		Primary analysis				Secondary analysis			
	Mean ± SE	% Change to control	Statistic	Df	Critical value	p-value	Statistic	Df	Critical value	p-value
Brain weight, perfused offspring (g)			Williams' test				Dunnett's test			
0	2.018 ± 0.021									
2	1.982 ± 0.021	-1.75	1.162	90	1.662	n.s.	-1.179	89	N/A	0.5049
10	1.954 ± 0.022	-3.15	1.876	90	1.737	<0.05*	-2.098	89	N/A	0.0986
50	1.908 ± 0.022	-5.45	3.347	90	1.76	<0.05*	-3.628	89	N/A	0.0014*
Brain weight, non-perfused offspring (g)			Williams' test ^a				Dunnett's test			
0	2.036 ± 0.014									
2	2.006 ± 0.015	-1.51	1.464	87	1.663	n.s.	-1.491	90	N/A	0.3164
10	1.965 ± 0.015	-3.52	3.105	87	1.736	<0.05*	-3.418	90	N/A	0.0021*
50	1.943 ± 0.016	-4.58	4.234	87	1.759	<0.05*	-4.316	90	N/A	0.0001*
Brain width (mm)			Williams' test				Dunnett's test			
0	15.34 ± 0.08									
2	15.13 ± 0.08	-1.39	1.664	89	1.662	<0.05*	-1.87	88	N/A	0.1583
10	15.05 ± 0.08	-1.93	2.183	89	1.739	<0.05*	-2.575	88	N/A	0.0316*
50	14.98 ± 0.08	-2.39	2.857	89	1.762	<0.05*	-3.185	88	N/A	0.0056*
Brain length (mm)			Dunnett's test				Williams' test			
0	20.89 ± 0.12									
2	20.95 ± 0.12	+0.3	0.371	88	N/A	0.9665	0.267	89	1.662	n.s.
10	21.02 ± 0.12	+0.65	0.793	88	N/A	0.7664	0.712	89	1.739	n.s.
50	21.17 ± 0.12	+1.37	1.68	88	N/A	0.2273	1.377	89	1.762	n.s.
Morphometrics – neocortex (mm)			Dunnett's test/t-test							
0	1.880 ± 0.020									
50	1.807 ± 0.020	-3.90	-2.592	37	N/A	0.0136*			N/A	
Morphometrics – hippocampus (mm)			Dunnett's test/t-test							
0	2.033 ± 0.028									
50	1.903 ± 0.028	-6.42	-3.343	37	N/A	0.0019*			N/A	
Morphometrics – corpus callosum (mm)			Dunnett's test/t-test							
0	0.289 ± 0.009									
50	0.256 ± 0.009	-11.42	-2.562	37	N/A	0.0146*			N/A	
Morphometrics – cerebellum (mm)			Dunnett's test/t-test							
0	0.855 ± 0.015									
50	0.852 ± 0.015	-0.35	-0.1779	37	N/A	0.8598			N/A	

317 Table 2. Re-analysis of brain weight, width, length, and morphometrics measures from the DNT study report in PND 66
318 offspring. Estimated Marginal Means were obtained from linear models with dose and sex as main effects, without
319 interaction; heteroscedasticity and litter as a random effect were included in the linear model for brain weight in non-
320 perfused animals only. Dunnett's test was based on these linear models. For Williams test, males and females were simply
321 pooled, as the test does not accommodate sex as a covariate. The effect direction in Williams' test was specified as "less"
322 for brain weight and brain width, and "greater" for brain length, based on effect size estimates from linear models. For
323 perfused offspring, no two pups were from the same litter. All statistical tests were performed on untransformed data
324 except for the cerebellum (log-transformed). ^a Williams' test performed on sex-balanced litter means - Bartlett's p=0.0097
325 indicated that Shirley's test should be used (p<0.01). Shirley's test did not return stable results, Williams' test is reported

326 *instead. * statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. SE – standard error. Df – degrees of freedom. n.s. – not significant i.e. $p > 0.05$.*
327 *N/A – not applicable*

328 Brain weight – non-perfused offspring

329 Table 1 shows summary statistics for the brain weights of non-perfused animals. Table 94 of the DNT
330 study report displays these results, with a statement that male and female mid and high dose groups
331 were different from control with $p < 0.01$, in statistical tests that were performed separately for sexes
332 and did likely not take into account the clustered nature of the data, i.e. more than one pup was
333 included from each litter. We replicated the test laboratory's statistical analysis. Spearman's
334 correlation indicated a monotonic dose-response relationship. As Bartlett's test resulted in $p < 0.01$,
335 using untransformed, square-root-transformed and logarithm-transformed data, the study methods
336 prescribed the non-parametric Shirley's test for a monotonic trend. For males, the mid and high
337 dose tested significantly differently from control. For females, all dose levels differed significantly
338 from control; the t' statistic and critical t' were 4.16 and 1.736 for the high dose group, 3.42 and
339 1.712 for the mid dose group, and 1.683 and 1.645 for the low dose group, respectively (all $p < 0.05$;
340 $n = 184$ animals). This latter finding is in conflict with the statistical results reported in the DNT study
341 report, in so far as the female low-dose effect was reported as not significant.

342 We modified the statistical analysis to include both sexes, and accommodate the clustered data
343 structure by specifying the litter as a random effect. This analysis confirms that at mid and high dose,
344 PND 66 offspring has a reduced brain weight compared to the control group (Table 2) using both
345 Williams' and Dunnett's test. The control group standard deviation was 0.067 g in both sexes,
346 encompassing the full variability of the study population *i.e.* both within and between litters. Effect
347 sizes in the mid and high dose groups exceed this level (1.1 and 1.4 * control group standard
348 deviation, respectively), while the statistically non-significant effect in the low dose group was 0.46 *
349 the control group standard deviation. The sensitivity analysis for Williams' test indicated statistical
350 significance also at the lowest dose level.

351 Brain width

352 Table 1 shows summary statistics for the brain width of perfused PND 66 offspring. These results are
353 included in the study report as part of Table 96, with a statement “Significant when compared to
354 control” at $p < 0.01$ for high dose males.

355 We replicated the test laboratory’s analysis. Williams’ test was indicated for males and Dunnett’s
356 test for females. In Williams’ test, the null hypothesis was rejected for mid and high dose males (mid
357 dose: $t' = 1.896$, t' -critical = 1.759, $p < 0.05$; high dose: $t' = 2.916$, t' -critical 1.779, $p < 0.05$). In
358 Dunnett’s test, the brain width of high dose males was significantly different from control ($p =$
359 0.0154). This finding is likely in conflict with the statistical results reported in the DNT study report,
360 in so far as Williams’ test was likely used in this situation, and statistically significant finding in males
361 at mid dose were not reported.

362 We then modified the statistical analysis to increase statistical power by including both sexes in the
363 same analysis. Williams’ test was indicated. Data for males and females were pooled for Williams’
364 test. In this test, brain width was significantly affected at all dose levels tested. This result was stable
365 in sensitivity analyses. In Dunnett’s test (*i.e.* not assuming a monotonic dose-response relationship),
366 only the mid and high dose levels were affected (Table 2). The magnitude of brain width decrease
367 was 1.4%, 1.9%, and 2.4% compared to control, in the low, mid, and high dose groups, respectively.
368 Expressed as Cohen’s d (*i.e.* multiples of control group standard deviations), the effect size was 0.60,
369 0.83, and 1.03, respectively.

370 Brain length

371 Table 1 shows summary statistics for the brain length of perfused PND 66 offspring. These results are
372 included in the study report as part of Table 96, with no statistically significant difference reported.

373 We replicated the test laboratory’s analysis. Dunnett’s test was indicated. We confirmed the
374 reported absence of a statistically significant effect in this analysis.

375 We then modified the statistical analysis to increase statistical power by including both sexes in the
376 same analysis. Dunnett's test was indicated. Neither Dunnett's nor Williams' test indicated statistical
377 significance (Table 2).

378 Brain morphometrics

379 For perfused animals, brain morphometrics summary data were included in table 97 of the DNT
380 study report for the control and high dose groups, with the with the statement "p≥0.05, no
381 statistical significance". Our replication of the test laboratory's analysis using Dunnett's test, which
382 simplifies to a t-test when only two groups are compared, indicated that the size of the
383 hippocampus in males, and of the corpus callosum in females, were decreased in a statistically
384 significant way in the high dose compared to the control group (p = 0.0186 and p = 0.0043,
385 respectively) (Table 1). These findings are in conflict with the statistical results reported in the DNT
386 study report.

387 The presence of statistically significant findings at high dose should trigger an evaluation of brain
388 morphometrics at the lower dose levels. However, morphometrics data for the low and mid-dose
389 level were not included in the study report.

390 We then re-analysed all morphometrics data, including males and females in the same linear model
391 to gain statistical power (Table 2). Accordingly, the neocortex, hippocampus and corpus callosum
392 were decreased by 3.9%, 6.4%, and 11.4% in treated compared to control animals, while the
393 cerebellum was not affected by treatment.

394 Summary of findings

395 In summary, the brain weight in adult (PND 66) offspring was affected by developmental fluazinam
396 exposure at 10 and 50 mg/kg bodyweight/day. Based on the largest dataset, the effect magnitude
397 was -3.5% and -4.6%, respectively, compared to the control group. At 2 mg/kg bw/day, a statistically
398 not significant effect of -1.5% was observed.

399 These effects were accompanied by a statistically significant decrease of brain width, but not brain
400 length, at all dose levels tested, with effect magnitudes of -1.4%, -1.9%, and -2.4% for the low, mid
401 and high dose, respectively. In addition, at high dose, linear corpus callosum, hippocampus, and
402 neocortex measures were decreased by -11%, -6.4%, and -3.9%, respectively, compared to control;
403 the cerebellum was not affected. Morphometrics measurements for the low and mid dose groups
404 were lacking.

405 No interaction of dose and sex on the effect size was observed for any of these endpoints.

406 When replicating the statistical analyses in the original study report, as described above, we found
407 statistically significant effects for the following endpoints, whereas the test laboratory reported
408 these as not statistically significant:

- 409 • Brain weights in perfused offspring at high dose, for females and likely also males;
- 410 • Brain weights in non-perfused offspring at low dose, for females;
- 411 • Brain width in perfused offspring at mid dose, for males;
- 412 • Thickness of the hippocampus in males;
- 413 • Thickness of the corpus callosum in females.

414 Jointly, these instances affected the conclusions of the test report. We paste here the full text of the
415 relevant conclusions section from the test report, with revisions based on our replicate analyses
416 indicated as ~~deletions~~ and additions.

417 “There was ~~not considered to be~~ any adverse effect of treatment on the morphological
418 development of the nervous system in the offspring. At 10 and 50 mg/kg/day brain weights
419 for male and female offspring, and at 2 mg/kg/day for female offspring, were lower than
420 Control, although statistical significance in the 2 and 10 mg/kg/day groups was only attained
421 for non-perfused offspring. ~~and v~~ Values in the 50 mg/kg/day groups for both sexes, and in
422 the male 10 mg/kg/day groups, were ~~consistent with~~ outside the Historical Control range.

423 Brain width amongst males at 10 and 50 mg/kg/day was also marginally but significantly
424 smaller than Control but was ~~again~~ within the Historical Control range. Microscopic
425 pathology and brain Morphometry assessments ~~did not~~ also suggest ~~any~~ adverse effect on
426 the nervous system with respect to the hippocampus in males and the corpus callosum in
427 females and, in the presence ~~absence~~ of supporting data from these investigations, the
428 differences in brain weight and width were ~~not~~ considered to represent an adverse effect of
429 treatment on the development of the nervous system.”

430 (Note: Historical Controls (HC) studies cannot be used to simply dismiss positive findings [32] but can
431 provide relevant information to a study. We have revised a HC statement above to include only the
432 five HCs inside a 5-year range centered at the current study [26,33].)

433 Discussion

434 **The principles of Good Laboratory Practices** require that reported results accurately and completely
435 reflect the raw data. The results of the replicate analysis reported above show how six analyses,
436 incorrectly reported as not statistically significant, collectively mask consistent effects across
437 multiple endpoints in the brains of adult offspring. This pattern suggests systematic and deliberate
438 misreporting of results, and constitutes an apparent violation of GLP principles and legal
439 requirements. It also violates widely accepted scientific and ethical standards.

440 The breaches of GLP raise questions as to the role of the responsible scientists. It also questions
441 whether existing inspection and enforcement mechanisms are adequate to ensure compliance or
442 detect non-compliance.

443 We reported most of the suspected GLP violations to EFSA in April 2026, and suggested a full GLP
444 audit of this study. Obviously, clarifications are needed regarding:

- 445 • Have brain morphometry data been obtained for the low and mid dose groups in PND 66
446 offspring, and are such data available? If so, then these need to be taken into account for
447 the present re-evaluation of fluazinam.
- 448 • Is the statistical output for all endpoints performed in the study report available, and are
449 there additional cases of unreported statistical significance?
- 450 • Are there differences in reported results and conclusions between the draft study report and
451 the final report? This could shed some light on the process leading up to the content of the
452 final report.
- 453 • What consequences does the apparently systematic non-compliance in this case have for
454 the regulatory acceptance of other studies from the same laboratory? It appears unlikely
455 that conclusions from all studies from this laboratory are false. On the other hand, it appears
456 unlikely that we have, by coincidence, identified the only such case. It will be a difficult, but
457 necessary task for regulatory agencies to re-evaluate all other studies from this laboratory to
458 the necessary depth.

459 A key source of conflict of interest in this system is the practice whereby companies commission and
460 fund studies of their own products. This creates a situation where commercial laboratories are
461 expected both to produce high-quality scientific reports and to satisfy clients with commercial
462 interests in favorable (i.e. null) findings. In a wider perspective, GLP principles seem insufficient to
463 reliably mitigate this issue. One possible remedy would be for regulatory agencies to commission
464 such studies, while the costs would continue to be borne by the companies [8,34].

465 The analyses presented in this paper could have far reaching regulatory consequences for fluazinam.
466 We recommend considering a potential classification of fluazinam for Reproductive Toxicity
467 Category 1B (*i.e.* presumed human reproductive toxicant, Repr. 1B). The following points are
468 relevant:

- 469 • In maternal animals, systemic toxicity (reduced body weight gain) was observed only at the
470 highest dose level. No neurotoxicity was observed in maternal animals.
- 471 • In offspring, systemic toxicity (reduced body weight and body weight gain) was also
472 observed and considered adverse (>10% difference from control) at the highest dose level
473 up to PND21, but not in older animals. On average across sexes, offspring body weight
474 decrements were -2.8%, -6.6%, and -15.7% in the low, mid and high dose groups compared
475 to control on PND 21, and +1.7%, -1.1%, and -4.4% on PND63. (Data assembled from Table
476 6.7.1-24 in the RAR, version July 2024)
- 477 • For comparison, offspring brain weight differences in the low, mid, and high dose groups
478 were -0,7%, -2,4%, and -4,8% on PND 21, and -1,7%, -3,2%, and -5,1% on PND66. Thus, while
479 the effect of fluazepam on offspring body weight diminished from PND 21 to PND 63, the
480 effect on brain weight remained stable or possibly slightly increased over the same period.
481 Similar is true for morphometrics and brain width measurements. These findings collectively
482 suggest an effect of fluazepam on offspring brain development that is independent of
483 maternal toxicity and not secondary to systemic toxicity or a general developmental delay
484 [35]. (Data assembled from Tables 6.7.1-33, 6.7.1-34, 6.7.1-36 in the RAR, version July 2024.
485 For brain weight, PND 66 results were averaged across the perfused and unperfused
486 datasets.)
- 487 • Statistically significant findings in PND 58-61 offspring included a decreased auditory startle
488 reflex in females at all dose levels tested (with a weaker, non-significant trend in males), and
489 an increased for learning and memory for males at all dose levels tested that were paralleled
490 by a similar effect, at high dose only, on PND 23/24. These have so far apparently not been
491 considered adverse [13]. Furthermore, the DNT properties in high dose male offspring on
492 PND 23/24, previously identified by the Working Group on Neurotoxicity (see below), should
493 be considered.

494 A classification as Repr 1B would trigger the legal cut-off criterion meaning that the approval for
495 fluazinam would not be renewed.

496 Another regulatory consequence relates to establishing toxicological Reference values such as the
497 Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI). In our re-analysis of the raw data using more sensitive statistical
498 approaches, we identified statistically significant decreases in adult offspring brain weight in the 10
499 and 50 mg/kg/day dose groups, together with a non-significant trend in the low dose group (2
500 mg/kg/day). We also found a statistically significant reduction in brain width at all tested dose levels.
501 Furthermore, among the morphometrics measurements obtained at the high dose, three out of four
502 evaluated brain regions showed statistically significant decreases, two of them with effect sizes
503 exceeding those observed for brain weight. Corresponding morphometric measurements at the low
504 and middle doses were not available (see Table 1).

505 Under these conditions, it is not possible to derive robust toxicological reference values, including an
506 acceptable daily intake. In our opinion, a Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level (LOAEL) of 2
507 mg/kg/day could potentially be set, based on statistically non-significant changes in brain weight
508 accompanied by significant changes in brain width, supported by behavioural effects observed at all
509 dose levels as described above.

510 Even under a less stringent assessment, in which 2 mg/kg/day is considered the No Observed
511 Adverse Effect Level (NOAEL) and no hazard classification based on DNT effects is concluded, the
512 present results would still have profound downstream implications for product approvals and risk
513 assessments. As DNT findings typically motivate an additional margin of exposure, an extra
514 assessment factor of 3 would plausibly be applied. Furthermore, acute reference values (Acute
515 Reference Dose ARfD, acceptable acute operator exposure levels AAOEL) would likely be aligned
516 with their chronic counterparts ADI and Acceptable Operator Exposure Level (AOEL), reflecting that
517 the observed effects result from exposure during a narrow but critical window of brain development
518 (e.g. [36]). Under this scenario, the currently proposed ADI and AOEL of 0.01 and 0.004 mg/kg/day

519 would likely change to 0.007 and 0.0025 mg/kg/day. The currently proposed ARfD and AAOEL of
520 0.07 and 0.025 mg/kg would likely change to 0.007 and 0.0025 mg/kg, respectively. Already under
521 the current proposal, one of three representative uses of fluazinam-containing products exceeds the
522 AOEL for resident children. It appears plausible that a decrease of reference values would lead to
523 additional uses to unacceptable exposures.

524 A third potential regulatory consequence is non-renewal. In the face of the evidence discussed
525 above, we consider it unlikely that fluazinam would have obtained approval in 2008 due to a lack of
526 an offspring NOAEL, if the study and its accurate results had been available to EU agencies at that
527 time.

528 Further, we consider it unlikely that fluazinam will receive renewed approval at the conclusion of the
529 ongoing evaluation, due to the lack of an offspring NOAEL for neurotoxicity and a potential
530 classification as Repr. 1B.

531 We furthermore identified a failure of agencies to detect apparent GLP violations and to request or
532 perform relevant analyses. Several specific occasions where the assessment by national or EU
533 agencies appears inadequate merit further discussion.

534 First, neither RMS nor EFSA or other member states identified incorrectly reported absence of
535 statistical significance across six related endpoints. Notably, we identified this issue not through
536 systematic replicate analyses but through observations of suspiciously large effect sizes in
537 morphometric outcomes (see Table 1) and subsequent follow-up analyses.

538 It is unclear why regulatory agencies did not identify this. One possibility is that the results were not
539 evaluated to the necessary depth.

540 Primary responsibility for ensuring correct reporting lies with the study director at the test
541 laboratory, and for accurate submission with the applicant company. However, because of its
542 reliance on industry-commissioned studies, the EU regulatory system for pesticides and other

543 chemicals has a structural vulnerability to biased analyses and incorrect reporting. The Peer Review
544 process, meaning member states and EFSA reviewing RMS's Assessment Report, does not seem to
545 reliably meet this challenge through thorough evaluation.

546 Second, in the initial evaluation by RMS, no effect on offspring brain weight was identified. In
547 response, we informed EFSA in October 2023 of the dose-dependent and sex-consistent effects,
548 supported by substantial effect sizes [13].

549 We also highlighted that, in the study report and in the Assessment Report, the statistically
550 significant of brain weight changes in the 10 and 50 mg/kg/day groups among non-perfused, but not
551 perfused offspring were presented as an inconsistency that implicitly introduces uncertainty in the
552 assessment and supports dismissal of the findings. However, this pattern is more likely an expected
553 consequence of the greater statistical power in the analysis of non-perfused compared with
554 perfused animals. We recommended that a new statistical analysis should properly accommodate
555 the litter effect, and that statistical power could be gained from combining male and female animals,
556 and including sex as a fixed factor to the model, given that the observed effect appears to be
557 independent of sex.

558 In July 2024, the "Neurotoxicity Working Group" discussed the presence and relevance of brain
559 weight effects in response to our letter. We here cite one section from the group's
560 recommendations to EFSA:

561 *"[Regarding significant -6.2% (males) and non-significant -3.5% (females) brain weight*
562 *changes at high dose on PND 21:] The WG experts, however, highlighted limitations in the*
563 *statistical analysis performed by the study authors on perfused brain weights, in that the*
564 *analysis was performed separately for males and females, while the brain weight effects*
565 *appear to be sex-independent. A higher statistical power could therefore be achieved by*
566 *applying the NAFTA guidance (2016), combining data from male and female animals and*
567 *assess the interaction between sex and treatment (see NAFTA, 2016). Further supporting the*

568 *biological relevance of this observation was the finding that at PND 66 (perfused rats) the*
569 *reduction in brain weight in female offspring at the top dose exceeded 1 standard deviation*
570 *(SD) relative to control females [control mean – 1SD mean (1.97-0.12 = 1.85) vs. top dose*
571 *mean (1.84)] (see EPA BMD guidance). In addition, the data from the non-perfused offspring*
572 *at PND 66 do not contradict the findings from the perfused animals.*

573 *The experts questioned the greater sample size of PND 66 brains non-perfused rats (40-*
574 *50/dose/sex vs. 10/dose/group for perfused animals). The larger sample size is the result of*
575 *treating multiple samples from each litter as independent measurements – which they are*
576 *not. The failure to properly account for litter effects (animals from the same litter were*
577 *pooled and no nested statistical analysis was conducted to account for the non-*
578 *independence of pups from the same litter) greatly influenced the probability of false*
579 *positives. Lack of proper/appropriate statistical analyses prevent use of this data for a*
580 *regulatory decision, as opposed to the data from perfused animals that were obtained using*
581 *a more validated/standardised protocol.”*

582 Accordingly, the Working Group rejected the statistical analysis of non-perfused PND 66 brain
583 weights that was included in the study report, noting that disregarding the litter effect inflates the
584 false positive rate. While this is true, this dataset definitely offers a greater statistical power,
585 because animals from 22-24, rather than 11-13, litters per sex per dose group were included (Table
586 1). Rather than performing or requesting a proper statistical analysis of this superior dataset, the WG
587 relied on the lower-powered analysis of brain weights in perfused animals, where no statistically
588 significant effect was reported.

589 This choice is questionable and consequential. If the most robust dataset has been analysed with
590 inappropriate methods, a correction should have been made. As shown in Table 2, appropriate
591 analysis of the brain weight of non-perfused adult offspring identified statistically significant effects
592 at 10 and 50 mg/kg/day. Furthermore, improving statistical power by analyzing female and male

593 animals together resulted in statistical significance at the same dose levels also for perfused adult
594 offspring brain weights.

595 Also, the effect size was 1.1 and 1.4 times the control group standard deviation of the mid and high
596 dose groups, respectively. The biological relevance of these large effects should have been
597 highlighted and discussed, because absence of statistical significance should not be the sole
598 rationale for lack of an effect [4].

599 It is worrying that the Working Group did not identify these effects, despite directly discussing the
600 relevant data and results. It is unclear why methodological limitations were recognized, yet no
601 independent reanalysis was performed or requested. Potential explanations include a general work
602 overload, insufficient resources, reluctance to correct an earlier assessment, an intention not to
603 further delay an assessment for a compound whose approval originally should have expired in 2019,
604 or insufficiently critical reliance on industry-reported results and conclusions.

605 Furthermore, it is unclear why apparently neither the Working Group, nor the Peer Review expert
606 meeting that received its input, considered a potential classification as Repr. 1B, following their
607 conclusion that fluazinam is a developmental neurotoxicant, based on effects observed at the
608 highest dose tested on brain weight, brain width, and the auditory startle reflex on PND 21/22), with
609 the brain width effect persisting into adulthood (PND 66) [15,16].

610 More broadly, RMS assembles the Assessment Report, and EFSA and all member states review it
611 under the peer review model applied in the EU. There is a recognized over-stretch of resources
612 across this regulatory system, and expertise is sometimes difficult to find, in particular for some
613 member states [37,38]. In this case, these insufficiencies may have contributed to a sequence of
614 incomplete evaluations and methodological errors, resulting in the failure to identify a clear effect of
615 fluazinam on brain weight in adult offspring.

616 Overall, the deviations from expected practices in this case suggest that the “peer review” process
617 for pesticide evaluations in the EU may not consistently deliver the intended level of protection for
618 human health and the environment.

619 Based on the findings, we encourage a discussion on improving the assessment criteria for brain
620 weight. Exposure to organophosphate insecticides, primarily via the diet, has previously been
621 estimated to cost between €46.8 billion to €194 billion annually in the EU through productivity
622 losses associated with IQ reduction [39]. The phasing out of lead (Pb) in fuel, paint and other
623 products resulted in IQ gains corresponding to an economic benefit through increased
624 productivity of US\$110 to 319 billion for each annual birth cohort in the US [40]. In addition to these
625 high socioeconomic costs of DNT effects, it is important to consider the individual suffering
626 associated with neurodevelopmental disorders. Given the potentially extensive consequences of
627 impaired neurodevelopment, the criteria used to determine whether observed effects are adverse
628 warrant careful scrutiny.

629 There seems to be no consensus regarding what effect magnitude on offspring brain weight might
630 be regarded adverse, or if such a threshold even exists. RMS initially applied a 10% cut-off for
631 adversity, meaning that a 9% chemical-induced reduction on brain weight would be considered
632 unproblematic.

633 For this threshold, RMS referred to a WHO guidance document [41], which suggests a coefficient of
634 variation of <10% between control groups from studies performed under the U.S. National
635 Toxicology Program as a “rough estimate for the threshold of adversity”.

636 Indeed, in the underlying studies conducted over a 16-year period in 22 different laboratories using
637 F344 rats obtained from seven suppliers, the coefficient of variation for brain weight in 90-day-old
638 rat offspring was 6.5% in males and 4.6% in females, rather than 10% [42]. It is unclear whether
639 either of these thresholds would ensure a level of protection against adverse effects that is
640 consistent with EU legal requirements. The most recent versions of the Assessment Report no longer

641 reiterate this cut-off. We suggest that EFSA and ECHA review the extent to which a 10% cut-off for
642 brain weight effects is being applied in risk assessments of other chemicals.

643 A 2012 guidance by the U.S. EPA suggests for the selection of a benchmark response level (BMR):

644 "In the absence of any other idea of what level of response to consider adverse, a change in
645 the mean equal to one control SD (or lower, e.g., 0.5 SD, for more severe effects) from the
646 control mean should be used."

647 In our opinion, considering the potentially life-long consequences of brain developmental deficits, an
648 effect of a chemical on brain weight, width and morphometrics qualifies as severe.

649 In humans, brain volume is weakly ($r = 0.24$) but consistently positively associated with IQ within
650 sexes [43]. However, no single aspect of brain volume (such as the number of a particular cell type,
651 or the size of a specific region) has been identified as responsible for this relationship. Similarly, in
652 the present DNT study of fluazepam, it is unclear which aspect or aspects of the brain underlie the
653 decreased brain weight observed in exposed animals, although the brain morphometrics may
654 provide insights to follow up on. It is therefore not possible to conclude a causal connection
655 between fluazepam exposure and decreases in IQ. However, the observed relationships make it
656 plausible that brain weight itself is an important endpoint to protect.

657 We suggest that if an effect on brain weight following developmental exposure is established at
658 doses that are not maternally toxic, and if the effect is not shown to be secondary to another well-
659 characterized effect, it would not be possible to derive a safe (non-adverse) effect size.

660 The overarching aim must be to ensure that developing brains are protected.

661 In response to our 2023 letter, the Assessment Report states: "Like other organ weight changes,
662 brain weight decreases without macroscopic, microscopic or functional correlations should be
663 interpreted with caution". This statement merits some discussion.

664 Generally, the presence of several coinciding effects increases the level of confidence in their true
665 existence. However, the developing brain is unlike other organs. The brain is among the most
666 complex structures in biology, with uniquely intricate developmental processes, and it is of
667 fundamental importance to the functioning of individuals and, indeed, human populations. The
668 protection of human offspring against neurodevelopmental toxicity should therefore aim not only to
669 prevent pathological effects, but also to preserve the full potential of the brain. It is thus motivated
670 to apply higher standards to the intactness of the developing brain compared to other organs. This is
671 also reflected in EU Regulation 1107/2009 where effects on the developing brain are singled out as
672 effects of particular significance that motivate an increased margin of safety.

673 Also, a guideline rodent DNT study tests only a small number of behaviours in a small number of
674 animals, often with significant variability in responses caused by biology and by challenges in
675 standardizing the experimental setup. In addition, only a few behaviours are evaluated. Behaviours
676 that are not measured in guideline DNT studies include e.g. social functions, anxiety and executive
677 functions. An absence of effects on behaviour in a standard guideline study may therefore simply be
678 a consequence of its limited scope and low statistical power.

679 Furthermore, in the present case of fluazepam, the statistical evaluation included in the study report
680 is inadequate. The repeated-measures structure of behavioural data has not been taken into
681 account, and behaviours were therefore analysed for each intra-session time point separately; sexes
682 were also analysed separately. One consequence of these choices is a loss of statistical power. In
683 addition, the control group for one of the included behaviours, the auditory startle response on PND
684 22/23, did not behave as expected. A lack of findings in the limited and poorly powered endpoints is
685 thus not equivalent to a lack of DNT properties. Requiring several related effects to be statistically
686 significant before they can be regarded as true or biologically relevant, in a situation where each
687 endpoint suffers from low power, does indeed reduce the ability of a study to identify true
688 developmental neurotoxicants.

689 In addition, several endpoints other than brain weight were indeed affected in a statistically
690 significant way. These include the brain width on PND 21 (high-dose males) and on PND 66 (both
691 sexes, all tested dose levels, as reported above); learning and memory in male offspring at the high
692 dose on day 23/24 and at all dose levels on PND 61; the auditory startle response on PND 23 in high
693 dose males; auditory startle response in females on PND 58 at all dose levels; and brain
694 morphometrics (as reported above).

695 In summary, we believe it is generally questionable, and non-protective to dismiss findings of effects
696 on brain weight when they are not accompanied by neuropathological or functional deficits.
697 Furthermore, in the case of fluazinam, several such correlates have been identified, and it is the
698 responsibility of the RMS to ensure that appropriate statistical analyses of the data are available for
699 the assessment.

700 Finally we foresee consequences for the policy proposal presently being discussed in the EU, the
701 “food and feed omnibus”: The omnibusproposes removing the current periodic renewal procedure
702 for active substances, by making approvals unlimited in most cases, with the possibility for targeted
703 or full re-evaluations. The current renewal model is said to absorb assessment capacity without a
704 corresponding gain in protection, because resources are spent on scheduled re-checks rather than
705 on specific concerns or new evidence. The proposal is said to maintain at least the current level of
706 protection, as freed resources could be used in a more targeted way. In addition, most currently
707 approved active substances have already been or are being renewed under the current regulation.
708 The current standard is therefore said to be very high [7,44].

709 In the present work, we have identified several cases in which a test laboratory wrongly reported the
710 absence of statistical significance. Regulatory agencies used excessively high effect size cut-offs for
711 biological relevance, failed to recognize important and likely consequential effects even when
712 directly confronted with such evidence and did not perform or request appropriate statistical

713 analyses even when poor practice was detected. All these events were related to a study that the
714 applicant company had withheld from EU agencies for 16 years [10].

715 These issues, all occurring in relation to a single study, call into question the purported “very high
716 standard” and indicate that the current assessment of pesticides does not reliably ensure the high
717 level of protection required by EU legislation.

718 We believe that a substantial increase in systematic scrutiny of company-sponsored studies and
719 assessments is needed to increase the standard and to achieve the intended level of protection
720 level. This should include studies and assessments that have already been evaluated previously. The
721 current periodic renewal procedure offers a framework for such systematic evaluations. The focus
722 for a discussion regarding a reform of the assessment system should be how to ensure sufficient
723 resources and capacity in regulatory agencies, not on reducing the possibility to re-evaluate.

724 While considering abandoning periodic re-evaluations of substances, the omnibus proposal adds
725 new options for the EU Commission to initiate targeted evaluations, *e.g.* in response to new
726 scientific developments or concerns. This is a welcome complement to systematic evaluation of
727 studies and assessments, but the use of these options will not be binding and the process by which
728 such evaluations should be triggered is unclear; hence the proposal does not seem to include a
729 resourced, systematic process needed to ensure the evaluation of company-produced studies and
730 assessments to the necessary depth.

731 Of note, our present findings are the result of applying current standard scientific practices to
732 existing data, not a consequence of any new scientific developments.

733 In consequence, unless the current binding re-approval system is replaced with another binding
734 scheme that leads to increased scrutiny of company-funded studies and assessments, we believe
735 that abandoning the period renewal will decrease the chances to reach the intended level of
736 protection.

737 Conclusions

738 We identified six instances in the Fluazinam study report in which statistically significant findings
739 related to PND66 brain endpoints were incorrectly reported as non-significant by the test laboratory.
740 Taken together, these errors materially affected the conclusions of the study report and contributed
741 to the overall conclusion of absence of DNT.

742 The pattern of incorrect analysis and reporting is recurrent and raises concerns about systematic
743 non-compliance with the law and GLP as well as established scientific and ethical standards, to the
744 detriment of health protection.

745 According to our re-analysis, data in the study report show evidence of treatment-related effects on
746 offspring brain development, and due to incomplete morphometric data at lower dose levels, we
747 argue that a NOAEL for neurotoxic effects in offspring brain cannot be reliably established.

748 Consequently, robust toxicological reference values, including an acceptable daily intake, cannot be
749 derived with sufficient confidence under the current dataset.

750 Reviewers at EFSA, the RMS, and in other member states did not identify the consistent dose-
751 dependent adverse effects in both sexes on adult offspring brain weight and brain width, supported
752 by effects on brain morphometry at the high dose level. This appears to be a consequence of
753 applying a questionable and non-protective cut-off criterion for reduced brain weight, as well as a
754 failure to perform or request appropriate statistical analyses facing inadequate company-provided
755 statistical analyses.

756 In light of the observed neurodevelopmental effects, we consider it unlikely that fluazinam will
757 ultimately receive renewed approval under the ongoing regulatory evaluation. Similarly, we doubt
758 that fluazinam would have obtained initial market approval, under the previous version of the
759 legislation in 2008, if these results had been known to agencies at that time. Consequently,

760 continued use since 2008 may have resulted in unnecessary and potentially harmful human
761 exposure, in the absence of full and correct disclosure of these neurodevelopmental hazards.

762 Given the uncertainties identified in the regulatory dataset and the evidence of previously
763 unrecognized DNT effects, reducing human exposure to fluazinam and other pesticides through
764 reduced use would be a prudent risk management approach until their safety can be established
765 with greater confidence. More broadly, this case highlights structural limitations in the current
766 regulatory testing system for pesticides, where studies are commissioned and funded by the
767 regulated industry. This creates an inherent conflict of interest that may not be fully mitigated by
768 GLP requirements alone, and it underscores the need for stronger independent oversight and review
769 capacity by regulatory agencies for existing studies. Future studies should be commissioned by
770 regulatory agencies to avoid this conflict of interest.

771 The case also raises questions about whether similar issues may exist in other studies from the same
772 laboratory, in studies from other laboratories, or for other endpoints and other types of chemicals.
773 These are important questions that warrant a broader, systematic evaluation of study practices and
774 overall regulatory study outputs for chemicals in the EU and other jurisdictions.

775 The EU “food and feed omnibus” proposal that is currently discussed, proposes to replace periodic
776 re-approval with largely unlimited approvals combined with the option of targeted re-evaluations,
777 and is particularly relevant in this context. The proposal is intended to increase efficiency and
778 redirect regulatory resources toward emerging concerns, in the face of lacking resources and
779 assessment capacity in EU member states. In our opinion, the starting point for a discussion on
780 reform of the assessment system should instead be how to ensure sufficient resources and capacity
781 in regulatory agencies. Consequently, unless the current binding re-approval system is replaced by
782 another binding scheme that will lead to increased scrutiny of company-funded studies and
783 assessments, we believe that abandoning periodic renewal will decrease the likelihood of achieving
784 the intended level of protection.

785 Overall, these findings suggest that current assessment procedures may not consistently ensure the
786 intended level of protection for human health and the environment.

- 787 • Ethics approval and consent to participate; Not applicable
- 788 • Consent for publication Not applicable
- 789 • Availability of data and materials; EU legislative documents were accessed from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/>. Dossiers, peer review reports (PRR) and assessment reports (AR) including
790 addenda were accessed from the Open EFSA portal at <https://open.efsa.europa.eu/>.
791 Minutes from Pesticide Peer Review meetings are available from
792 [https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-12/minutes-ppr-mammalian-
793 toxicity.pdf](https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-12/minutes-ppr-mammalian-toxicity.pdf). Recent updates to the Renewal Assessment Report for Fluazinam, and of
794 Appendix 2 to the Peer Review teleconference 183 (Advice from the Working Group on
795 Neurotoxicity) were obtained from the Swedish Chemicals Agency.
796
797 The data that underly the main findings of this study, i.e. the full DNT study report of
798 fluazinam, is available from EFSA upon request under the EU transparency rules (Regulation
799 (EU) 2019/1381). The scripts/code that were used for the statistical re-analyses and
800 additional analyses are available from the authors upon request.
- 801 • Competing interests; AM has provided paid expert testimony for plaintiff in a litigation
802 related to the DNT of the insecticide chlorpyrifos, Superior Court of California, County of
803 Monterey, Case No. 19CV002262. AM and CR have provided a statement to the General
804 Court of the EU in relation to the DNT of the insecticide chlorpyrifos-methyl, case number T-
805 77/20, upon request of the environmental organisation “Health and Environment Alliance”
806 (HEAL), in 2021, as part of their employment. AM and CR have provided a statement to the
807 General Court of the EU in relation to the potential DNT of glyphosate, case number Case T-
808 639/24, upon request by the environmental organisation “Pesticide Action Network”, in

809 2024, as part of their employment. AM and CR have also provided expert testimony related
810 to pesticide exposure from organic and conventional foods in Swedish Patent and Market
811 Courts, case no. PMT11299–16, in 2017, as part of their employment.

812 • Funding; Open access funding provided by Stockholm University. This work was carried out
813 in the framework of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
814 (PARC) and has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and
815 innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057014. Views and opinions
816 expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of
817 the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union
818 nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The work was also co-funded by
819 FORMAS, The Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development, grant number 2023-
820 00816.

821 • Authors' contributions; A.M. was responsible for the original idea, extracted the raw data
822 from the DNT study report and conducted the statistical analyses. A.M. and C.R. developed
823 the manuscript jointly. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

824 • Acknowledgements; Not applicable

825 • Authors' information (optional); Not applicable

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